

Task 4.1A (Subtask 3): The RADx Global Code Book Ontology

Technical Report

Owner: Stanford University

Revision History

Date (YYYY-MM-DD)	Version Number	Revision Reviewed / Approved By	Brief Description of Change
May 29, 2025	v1	Stanford University team	Initial version

Purpose

This report describes the RADx Global Code Book Ontology. This Ontology provides a formally structured vocabulary to describe the Tier 1 Common Data Elements (CDEs) that are defined in the RADx Global Code Book.

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Purpose and Motivation

The RADx Common Data Elements Ontology, known as the **Global Code Book Ontology (GCBO)**, and referred to as such from now on, provides a formally structured vocabulary that captures the semantics of the data elements used across the RADx program. Its central purpose is to:

Formalize the RADx Common Data Elements Using Ontological Terms

The GCBO encodes the RADx Common Data Elements as ontology terms that unambiguously specify the intended meaning of each element. Rather than treating data elements as mere labels or column headers, the ontology defines each one as a concept with clearly described semantics, logical structure, and relationships to other terms. This formalization enables machine-readable interpretation and supports semantic interoperability across data systems and tools.

Clarify and Disambiguate the Meaning of RADx Common Data Elements

Each data element is defined with precise descriptions that reduce ambiguity and make the intended use and scope of the element explicit. This benefits both technical and non-technical users by ensuring consistent understanding and interpretation of terms during data collection, analysis, and reuse.

Support Terminological Consistency Through Synonyms and Labels

To account for variations in terminology used by different teams or tools, the GCBO includes synonyms, alternate labels, and abbreviations associated with each CDE. These mappings support alignment across datasets, user interfaces, documentation, and submission templates, fostering consistency in data representation.

Provide a Reference for Acronyms and Controlled Vocabulary Terms

The ontology also maintains a reference glossary of commonly used acronyms, linking them to their expanded forms and associated ontology concepts. This

enhances clarity and promotes standardized use of terms across documentation, metadata records, software interfaces, and communications.

Provide a Classification of RADx Common Data Elements Based on Domain Concepts

The ontology logically defines several core classifications of RADx Common Data Elements based on domain specific concepts. For example, the ontology classifies a subset of CDEs as Cancer Data Elements, which are themselves classified as Disease Data Elements. This classification is performed by automated reasoning.

Design Principles and Scope

The **Global Code Book Ontology (GCBO)** was developed to meet the specific semantic and informational needs of the RADx program's data harmonization and standardization efforts. Its design was guided by a set of **competency questions**—natural language questions that articulate the types of information the ontology should be able to represent, organize, and clarify.

Competency questions help to define the **scope and structure** of an ontology by revealing which concepts are important to users, how those concepts are interrelated, and where semantic clarification is most needed. In the case of the GCBO, these questions were crafted to reflect the real-world needs of researchers, data curators, software engineers, and program administrators who interact with RADx metadata, study submissions, and the Global Code Book itself.

Common data element corpus

- What is the list of Tier 1 common data elements in RADx?
- Which common data elements are related to respiratory conditions?
- Which common data elements are related to immune systems diseases?

Common data element structure

- What is the identifier for a given common data element?
- What is the human readable description for a given common data element?
- What are the values that a given common data element may take?

Variable values

- What common data elements is a given value used for?
- What does a data value of "1" mean in the context of a given common data element?

This question-driven methodology ensured that the GCBO was not developed in the abstract but was instead grounded in the practical needs and workflows of its users. Each competency question directly informed the ontology's structure,

helping to prioritize which terms needed precise definitions, formal relationships, synonym support, and clear documentation.

By aligning ontology development with these user-centric questions, the GCBO provides a coherent and purpose-built vocabulary that facilitates accurate data interpretation, metadata quality, and semantic alignment across the RADx ecosystem.

What the Ontology Is Not Intended to Cover

While the Global Code Book Ontology (GCBO), plays a crucial role in formalizing and clarifying the meaning of RADx CDEs, it has been developed with a deliberately focused scope. To maintain precision, relevance, and usability, the ontology intentionally excludes certain areas.

The GCBO is not intended to serve as a comprehensive biomedical ontology. It does not aim to cover the full breadth of clinical, laboratory, or epidemiological concepts in the broader biomedical or COVID-19 research landscape. Instead, its scope is purposefully narrowed to concepts directly relevant to the standardized elements defined in the RADx Common Data Elements framework.

Ontology Term Curation and Definition Development

After defining the initial set of competency questions, we conducted a careful review to determine which questions were within scope for the first release of the RADx Common Data Elements (CDEs) Ontology. This step allowed us to prioritize questions that directly aligned with core user needs and that could be feasibly supported by available data and documentation.

For each selected competency question, we analyzed its underlying informational requirements to identify the key concepts that needed to be represented in the ontology. These included both primary terms—such as “Common Data Element,” “Tier 1 variable” — and supporting terms that provide context.

Curating and Structuring Ontology Terms

Once the relevant terms were identified, we curated them into a structured vocabulary, organizing concepts by type and role. For example:

- **Common Data Elements (CDEs)** were modeled as distinct ontology classes, each associated with definitions, labels, and logical properties that support interpretation and reuse.
- **Permissible values** for categorical variables were represented using value sets and enumeration constructs within the ontology, allowing for explicit semantic description of allowable entries.

We then established a consistent modeling pattern for each concept type to promote coherence and reusability across the ontology. This design included decisions about class hierarchies, property usage, and annotation standards to support interoperability and clarity.

Automated Construction of OWL Axioms

To scale the process of ontology population and minimize manual effort, we developed a custom Java program that ingests data from the **RADx Global Code Book Data Dictionary**—the central spreadsheet used to define CDEs—and transforms that information into structured OWL (Web Ontology Language) axioms.

This program extracted definitions, labels, synonyms, permissible values, and other metadata directly from the Data Dictionary and encoded them into ontology terms using OWL constructs such as `rdfs:label`, `rdfs:comment`, `owl:equivalentClass`, and `skos:altLabel`. This approach ensured alignment between the GCBO and the authoritative source of CDE definitions, while also enabling regular updates as the Data Dictionary evolves.

This curated and semi-automated approach to term development ensures that the GCBO is both grounded in practical usage and aligned with semantic web standards, facilitating its integration into tools, metadata systems, and data governance workflows across the RADx program.

Ontology Content Summary and Structure

The RADx Global Code Book Ontology is organized into a set of logical subsets that reflect the structural and semantic roles of terms within the broader Common Data Elements framework. These subsets help maintain clarity, modularity, and consistency across the ontology while supporting the formalization of meaning for standardized data elements used in RADx data collection efforts.

Ontology Subsets

1. Data Elements

The data element subset (subclasses of `DataElement`) contains classes that represent the individual standardized data elements used across RADx studies. Each class in this subset corresponds to a distinct variable or field used in data collection instruments—such as "participant age," "autoimmune disease or disorder," or "have trouble walking." These terms are formally defined, uniquely identified, and enriched with semantic annotations to ensure that their meaning is unambiguous, reusable, and machine-readable.

2. Data Element Sections

The data element subset (subclasses of `DataElementSection`) includes classes that define logical groupings of data elements. These groupings correspond to sections commonly found in structured data collection instruments or metadata templates, such as "Demographics," "Test Information," or "Clinical History." This subset provides an organizing layer that supports both ontology navigation and interface-level rendering of forms, while also reinforcing the semantic cohesion of related data elements.

3. Data Element Values

The data element subset (subclasses of `DataElementValue`) models the enumerated or controlled values that may appear as responses to particular data elements. Each class in the `DataElementValue` subset represents a specific

permitted value—such as "Yes," "No," "Positive," or "Unknown"—and is linked to the relevant data element via OWL annotations. By formalizing these value sets, the ontology enables consistent data validation, integration, and interpretation across systems and datasets.

4. Domain specific concepts

The domain specific subset contains a broad range of domain-relevant reference concepts that provide semantic context for data elements. These are not data elements themselves but include entities such as diseases, conditions, symptoms, and population descriptors—concepts that are used to define or annotate data elements more precisely. `OtherThing` serves as an organizational superclass to prevent excessive proliferation of unrelated top-level ontology classes, while still making these contextual terms available for linking and reasoning.

Modeling Standards and Annotation

All terms in the ontology are modeled as OWL classes, using semantic web standards to support interoperability, clarity, and reuse. Each class is annotated with:

- `rdfs:label` for human-readable preferred names
- `skos:definition` for formal, genus-differentia-style definitions
- `skos:altLabel` for synonyms, abbreviations, or alternative expressions

This structured approach ensures that the ontology is both semantically precise and practically usable, enabling accurate metadata creation, consistent interpretation of variables, and improved discoverability and alignment of RADx data across tools, documentation, and workflows.

Availability

The RADx Common Data Element ontology has been published in BioPortal with an ontology acronym of GCBO (for Global Code Book Ontology). It can be viewed and downloaded from BioPortal at: <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/GCBO>

Figure 2 – The RADx Common Data Element Ontology, or Global Code Book Ontology, is published in BioPortal. Information about the ontology and the classes can be browsed using the BioPortal User Interface.

Conclusions and Future Work

The RADx Global Code Book Ontology (GCBO) provides a structured and semantically clear way to represent the Tier 1 Common Data Elements defined in the RADx Global Code Book. By formalizing data elements as OWL classes with uniform annotations, the ontology supports clearer communication, improved metadata quality, and better alignment across RADx tools and documentation.

Designed with a focused scope and guided by practical competency questions, the GCBO emphasizes clarity and usability. Its subset structure—covering data elements, value sets, sections, and contextual concepts—helps organize content in a way that reflects real-world usage while keeping the ontology manageable and coherent.

Importantly, the approach taken here—transforming a data dictionary into a formal ontology—can be applied well beyond the RADx program. This method provides a generalizable strategy for enhancing the semantic clarity and interoperability of structured datasets in other research domains or large-scale data collection efforts.

Future work may include refining term definitions, extending coverage where needed, and enhancing tooling for ontology-driven metadata support. As RADx data practices evolve, the GCBO offers a foundation to support consistent, well-defined terminology across the program.

Resources

- RADx Global Code Book Ontology in BioPortal
<https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/GCBO>
- RADx Data Dictionary to Ontology Code on GitHub
<https://github.com/bmir-radx/radx-dict2ont>